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ENHANCED STABILITY AND CONTROLLED RELEASE OF EUCALYPTUS ESSENTIAL OIL VIA ULVAN-BASED MICROPARTICLES FOR FUNCTIONAL FISH FEEDS

Nikoletta TRICHA^{1*}, Chrysanthos STERGIPOULOS², Sofia PAPADAKI¹, Anna MOUSTOGIANNI³ and Magdalini KROKIDA²

¹DIGNITY Private Company, 30-32 Leoforos Alexandrou Papagou, Zografou, 157 71 Athens, Greece

²Laboratory of Process Analysis and Design, School of Chemical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Iroon Polytechniou 9, 157 80 Athens, Greece

³ZOONOMI SA, 102 Thesi Kritika, 200 06 Vrahati Korinthias, Greece

*Corresponding author, e-mail: nikoletta.tricha@gmail.com

Introduction: Phytobiotics, such as eucalyptus essential oil, boost farmed fish immunity, but their volatility limits feed use. Ulvan, a sulfated polysaccharide from *Ulva lactuca*, microencapsulates bioactives to enhance stability and delivery.

Aims: This study developed ulvan–lecithin microparticles for stabilizing and controlling the release of EEO in functional fish feed formulations.

Materials and Methods: The emulsion of ulvan (5% w/v), EEO (10% w/w), and lecithin (1% w/w) was homogenized (15,000 rpm, 10 min), ultrasonicated (5 min), and freeze-dried. Particle size was measured with DLS. Encapsulation efficiency was assessed via hexane extraction and GC-MS. FTIR and DSC were used to characterize the structural and thermal properties. *In vitro* release and kinetic modeling were performed in PBS (RT, 100 rpm, 24 h). 1.7 mm pellets with 0.1% w/w microparticles were aged at 45 °C, 70% RH for 28 days. Feeds were analyzed for moisture, protein, lipids, antioxidants, and phenolics.

Results: Microparticles showed $76.4 \pm 1.2\%$ encapsulation and 145 μm mean diameter. FTIR confirmed stable polymeric interactions; DSC showed Tg shifts due to lecithin (+22.6 °C) and oil (–17.3 °C). Release followed Korsmeyer–Peppas kinetics, with 63.9% at 6 h and 90.2% at 24 h. Encapsulated feeds showed lower moisture gain (9.8% vs 12.0%), protein loss (–1.65% vs –3.5%), lipid degradation (–4.17% vs –12.5%), and better antioxidant (–13.5% vs –29%) and phenolic retention (–16% vs –34%).

Conclusion: Ulvan–lecithin microparticles enhanced the stability and controlled release of eucalyptus oil, improving the shelf life and functional quality of aquafeeds. This green system supports sustainable fish nutrition and the valorization of marine biomass.

Keywords: Aquafeed, Eucalyptus essential oil, Microencapsulation, Ulvan

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